

Studies on the Fries Rearrangement. Part II*

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The reaction temperature, nature and amount of the catalyst, nature of the solvent, and nature and size of the acyl group have been studied in the Fries transposition.

In continuation of our work (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 881) on the course of the Fries rearrangement, we have investigated the rearrangement of 2-bromo-4-methylphenyl acetate, phenyl- β -cyclohexyl propionate, and phenyl- γ -cyclohexyl butyrate under the following conditions:

(a). (i) At 100° in presence of a solvent, and (ii) at 110° without a solvent, using anhydrous aluminium chloride, zinc chloride, stannic chloride, ferric chloride, and boron trifluoride as catalysts.

(b). With aluminium chloride (i) at 110° in different molecular proportions, and (ii) at different temperatures.

At 100° in nitrobenzene and at 110° without solvent, the phenyl- β -cyclohexyl propionate and phenyl- γ -cyclohexyl butyrate gave mainly *p*-hydroxy ketones. In the case of the former 13% of *o*-hydroxy and 51% of *p*-hydroxy ketones were obtained when CS₂ was used as a solvent, but at 140°, it furnished 60% of the *ortho* isomer and none of the *para* isomer (Table IV).

Effect of the proportion of the catalyst was studied using 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 3.0, and 4.0 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride on the above esters. In all cases the reaction was carried out at 110°, without any solvent, for 2 hours. The rearrangement was found best when 3 moles of the catalyst were used (Table III). Benzene was found to act as a better solvent than nitrobenzene, toluene or CS₂ (Table IV). Regarding the catalysts, aluminium chloride was found to be the best (Table I).

*Part I: This *Journal*, 1958, 35, 881.

At low temperature cyclohexanepropionyl and cyclohexanebutyryl groups migrated to *para* position, but at higher temperatures, migration to *ortho* position took place (Table II).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Bromo-4-methylphenyl acetate was prepared as usual (Tiwari and Singh, *loc. cit.*) from 2-bromo-4-methylphenol (20 g.) and acetyl chloride (10 g.); b.p. 120°/3mm, yield 60%. (Found: C, 47.12; H, 3.92. $C_9H_9O_2Br$ requires C, 47.16; H, 3.93%.)

Phenyl- β -cyclohexyl propionate and *phenyl- γ -cyclohexyl butyrate* were prepared as usual (Tiwari and Singh, this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 496; *loc. cit.*).

Rearrangement in Presence of Solvent

Nitrobenzene.—The reaction was carried out in the usual manner by taking aluminium chloride (anhyd., 1.5 *M*), freshly distilled nitrobenzene (15 c.c.), and esters (1 *M*). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hours. *o*-Hydroxy ketones and nitrobenzene were separated from the mixture by steam distillation and subsequently the ketones were isolated and characterised in the usual way (Tiwari and Tripathi, *ibid.*, 1954, **31**, 841). The residue left after steam distillation was worked up for *p*-hydroxy ketones.

Benzene.—The ester (1 *M*) was suspended in benzene (15 c.c.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5 *M*) was added to it. The reaction was carried out on a water bath for 2 hours and was worked up for the isolation and characterisation of hydroxy ketones in the usual way (Tiwari and Singh, *loc. cit.*) (Table IV).

Toluene & Carbon Disulphide.—The rearrangements in toluene and in CS_2 were studied as in the case of benzene.

Rearrangement in Absence of Solvent

Fries rearrangement of the esters were carried out with anhydrous aluminium chloride, zinc chloride, stannic chloride, and ferric chloride as catalysts (1.5 *M*) in the usual way. In the case of boron trifluoride as catalyst, the temperature was maintained at 100°, and after decomposition with HCl (dil.) and ice, the product was steam distilled; the *o*-hydroxy ketone from the distillate and the *p*-hydroxy ketone from the residue were isolated and characterised in the usual way (Karl *et al.*, *Chem. Ber.*, 1954, **87**, 194; Tiwari and Singh, *loc. cit.*) (vide Table I).

TABLE I

Effect of different catalysts in nitrobenzene.

Ester taken = 2 g. Heated at 100° for 2 hrs.

No.	Ester.	Ketone.	$AlCl_3$.	$ZnCl_2$.	$SnCl_4$.	$FeCl_3$.	BF_3 .
1.	2-Bromo-4-methylphenyl acetate	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy	1.8 g.	1.7 g.	1.4 g.	1.1 g.	1.6 g.
	Phenyl- β -cyclohexyl propionate	<i>p</i> - "	1.4	1.3	1.0	0.3	1.0
3.	Phenyl- γ -cyclohexyl butyrate	<i>p</i> - "	1.5	1.3	1.1	0.5	0.7

Effect of the Proportion of the Catalyst

Rearrangement of 2-bromo-4-methylphenyl acetate, phenyl- β -cyclohexyl propionate, and phenyl- γ -cyclohexyl butyrate was carried out at 110° without solvent, using 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 3.0, and 4.0 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride for 2 hours as usual.

TABLE II
Ester taken = 2 g.

* Ester.	Ketone.	Amount of anhydrous aluminium chloride (in M).					
		0.25	0.5.	1.0.	1.5.	3.0.	4.0.
1.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy	Nil	Nil	Traces	1.8 g.	1.9 g.	1.5
2.	{ <i>p</i> - <i>o</i> - " "	Nil X	Nil X	Nil X	1.0 Traces	1.3 X	1.2 X
3.	<i>p</i> - " "	Nil	Nil	Nil	1.2	1.5	1.2

* The number corresponds to those in Table I.

Effect of Temperature

The effect of temperature was studied in the case of the three esters without solvent and keeping temperature at 100°, 110°, 120°, and 140° for 2 hours as usual.

TABLE III
Ester taken = 2 g. AlCl₃ = 1.5 M.

* Ester.	Ketone.	100°.	110°.	120°.	140°.
1.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy	Traces	1.8 g.	1.7 g.	1.4 g.
2.	{ <i>o</i> - <i>p</i> - " "	X X	X 1.0	0.9 Traces	1.2 X
3.	{ <i>o</i> - <i>p</i> - " "	X X	X 1.2	0.5 X	1.1 X

* Same as in Table I.

Effect of Solvent

The rearrangement of the esters was carried out in the different solvents, viz., nitrobenzene, CS₂, benzene, and toluene on a steam bath.

TABLE IV
Ester taken = 2 g. AlCl₃ = 1.5 M.

* Ester.	Ketone.	C ₆ H ₅ NO ₂ .	CS ₂ .	C ₆ H ₆ .	C ₇ H ₈ .
1.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy	1.8 g.	1.8 g.	1.9 g.	1.2 g.
2.	{ <i>o</i> - <i>p</i> - " "	1.4	0.3 1.0	1.3	0.9
3.	<i>p</i> - " "	1.5	1.3	1.3	0.8

* Same as in Table I.

TABLE V

* Ester.	B. P.	Yield.	o-Hydroxy ketones.				2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone.				
			Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
1.	126-27°/2mm	89%	C ₉ H ₉ O ₂ Br	47.11	47.16	3.92	3.93	258°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ Br	13.68	13.69
3.	220°/5	55	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₂	78.10	78.17	8.92	8.95	125°	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₄	13.15	13.15.

* Number same as in Table I.

The physical data of phenyl- γ -cyclohexyl butyrate and *o*- and *p*-hydroxy ketones derived from phenyl- β -cyclohexyl propionate have been recorded in previous papers (*loc. cit.*).

The authors wish to thank Dr. A. B. Sen, Head of the Chemistry Department, for his kind help in this work.

One of the authors (A. Singh) is very much thankful to the Research Grant Committee, U. P., for the award of a research assistantship.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received October 29, 1959